

Sequence to Sequence Neural Machine translation from Danish to English analysis of ANKI and European Parliament corpus (November 2025)

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Abstract— This paper is an empirical study of the two common corpora for Neural Machine Translation, Anki and European Parliament corpus. Our focus was on Danish to English translation by applying state-of-the-art tools for translation. During this process, we found several challenges, such as AVX and TensorFlow versions; long complex morphology that cannot capture accurate translation. The Danish language itself is a challenge because of its confounded morphology. We then present our modified Attention Alignment Score function, which is showing promising result in Danish to English Neural Machine Translation.

Index Terms— Artificial intelligence, Artificial neural networks, Neural Machine Translation, Semi supervised learning

I. INTRODUCTION

NEURAL network for Machine Translation started in 2014 with the publication of the paper “*Sequence to Sequence Learning with Neural Networks*” by Sutskever et al. [1] followed in the same year by Bahdanau et al [2] that focuses on the “*Encoder/Decoder*” structure. Papers published after this discovery, build around the concept of RNN or ANN, to predict a tensor by decoding and encoding two sequences.

However, to begin a Neural Translation, researchers need a corpus containing a source language and a target language. This is often denoted as a parallel corpus. This parallel corpus is tokenized at a sentence level. The final stage is to transform the text into numbers and create a lookup dictionary, for later transformation from numbers to text. Then padded to have the same sentence length, since two languages often do not have the same amount of words in a sequence.

An issue with this structure is that semantic information is lost. The model, therefore, is only as strong as the amount of data fed to the model. However, in 2015 Bahdanau et al. published Encoding-Decoding with Attention [3] followed by “*Attention is all you need*” in 2017 [18], the concept is to capture semantic information. The attention transformer concept focuses on specific parts of the input sequence at each

time step, which has shown significant improvement for Neural Machine Translation.

Since 2014 Sequence to Sequence Neural Machine Translation has been used in; English to Vietnamese (2017) [4]; English to Persian (2017) [5]; Chinese-Uyghur (2017) [6]; Japanese to Chinese (2017) [7]; Chinese-Catalan (2019) [8] used the UN corpus; Six Indian Languages (2019) [9]. However, we have been unable to find research specifically about Scandinavian language translation, this is not because of a lack of resources. The UN data¹ and the European Parliament² have both published parallel corpus containing Scandinavian languages.

Therefore, this is the first paper to our knowledge that applies the European Parliament corpus onto state-of-the-art Neural Machine Translation tools from Keras and Google's TensorFlow with a focus on Danish to English Neural Machine Translation.

This research aims to provide an overview of Danish to English sequence to sequence NMT and provide an overview of our findings. Our original method approach was to use the European Parliament corpus and develop a model for translation Danish to English. To our surprise, we could not make the models work. After several testing and model building, we decided to try and modify the Alignment Score. This had an unexpected result on the performance, as well as seemed to improve the translation. But before we continue let us introduce the corpus ANKI and European Parliament.

II. CORPUS

The corpus ANKI (<https://www.manythings.org/anki/>) before using this, it is advisable to remove the third column. It contains irrelevant information that Keras and Google NMT cannot recognize in the text pre-processing stage. We used MSExcel for this process. The Danish to English corpus consists of 20,376 sentences, this is a limitation to how many unique words are in the corpus. Thus, the European Parliament corpus could be a better choice since it offers more complex sentences (see Table II and Table III for comparison).

The corpus from the European Parliament (EuroP - www.statmt.org/europarl/) are divided into two files an Input

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¹ <https://cms.unov.org/UNCorpus/>

² <https://www.statmt.org/europarl/>

language and an Output language in the form of English. We modified the Tensorflow and Keras code, so it could handle two separate files. This seemed to degrade the performance, which resulted in a very low text pre-processing stage. As well as being a time-consuming process of modifying this stage. Thus, we decided to combine UK and DK in EuroP with MSEExcel. The combined corpus does contain a range of issues, as well as the Danish special characters: æøå. These we replaced æ with aa; ø with oe; and å with aa.

We would also like to point out that the corpus from the European Parliament has issues, such as very complex translations and certain parliament code, an example: (B5-0164/2000). That was a challenge for the text pre-processing stage to capture and often gave an error. These we had to remove manually.

There were also issue with translation from Danish to English, in Table I we have given an overview of four items, but there are many more. As can be seen in the table; Issue 1, there is a lack of “Nos” in the Danish translation. Issue 2 is an example of the Danish language using one-word and English using two-word. This issue should be correct or caught by the attention mechanism, however, the European Parliament long sentences could present a challenge for the model without attention. Issue 3 is an example of the issues regarding “-0” vs “- 0” – these could be the reason for the low performance of the European Parliament corpus. Regarding Issue 4 here “*at 12 noon*” has been translated into “*i morgen middag*”. The corpus itself was not intended for machine translation, meaning the translation is made to increase readability. This is later found to be a significant barrier.

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF ISSUES FOUND IN CORPUS FROM EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

Issue	DK	UK
1	Kommissionen kan ikke acceptere ændringsforslag 15, 28, 29 og 32.	The Commission cannot accept Amendments Nos 15, 28, 29 and 32.
2	Miljølovgivning	Environmental legislation
3	(B5 -0014/2000 og B5 0208/2000)	(B5 - 0014/2000 and B5 0208/2000)
4	Afstemningen finder sted i morgen middag.	The vote will take place tomorrow at 12 noon

However, before we continue, we wanted to share our experience with some challenges we face when setting up the testing environment.

III. THE CHALLENGES

The major challenge we faced was AVX (Advanced Vector eXtensions). This is a CPU architecture that computers and server after 2016-2018 will have. We purchased three older computers in 2017 to run our NMT testing. These did not have AVX. Running TensorFlow after version 1.15.0, on a CPU without AVX support, and Python will generate an overflow or buffer error – which is an ambiguous statement that took a

significant amount of time for us to realize, was due to a CPU error and not programming error in our modelling.

To solve this issue of AVX, we experimented with different solutions, such as Google Colab, Machine Learning Cloud, Google Docker Swarm.

Google Colab provides up to a most of 24GB ram. This worked fine with smaller text, such as with ANKI length. But,

TABLE II
SHOWS ANKI SENTENCES LENGTH FROM 4000 TO 19000 SENTENCES

ANKI	Input	Output	Max Input	Max Output
S-4000	71	77	22	40
S-8000	76	79	27	50
S-16000	80	85	40	91
S-19000	83	86	57	91

TABLE III
SHOWS EUROPEAN SENTENCES LENGTH FROM 4000 TO 19000 SENTENCES

EUROP	Input	Output	Max Input	Max Output
S-4000	94	95	759	788
S-8000	100	100	759	788
S-16000	107	109	1013	929
S-19000	108	109	1013	929

with the European Parliament, that has a sentence length of up to 700 words, meant disaster for the processing in Colab. Resulting in out of memory. Even with 4000 sentences.

Alternatively, we experimented using Pay-as-you-use Data such as Azure, AWS and Google Cloud (GC). We tested with Google Cloud Kubernetes and VM solution to run the NMT. We found that GC keeps data for 24hours, then resets and delete containers and images. Thus, the GC is a volatile environment and therefore, not a recommended location to run NMT.

Most of our development and experimentation was performed on our main windows2016 server with Hyper-V. Here we installed Anaconda to create a test environment. It worked fine for a time until updates from Anaconda started to deteriorate the functionality. Afterwards, we started to experiment with Docker Swarm. The Swarm was running on the Windows2016 in a virtual machine running Linux Mint. The Hyper-V environment increased the speed of training the models, with about 10-20 min depending on the size of the training set. This Linux OS is where we installed Docker and created a container with Jupyter, Python3 and TensorFlow 1.15.0. The result of this experiment was higher performance compared to Anaconda and Google Cloud. Running the containers and images from Docker, on a virtual machine, meant that we could take snapshots and restore the Docker Swarm to its original state. Thus, ensuring a reduction in loss of containers and images when the main server would restart. It is an easily scalable environment, where the requirement of the other servers is a Linux operating system (such as RancherOS) with installed Docker.

Yet, the server we bought was older and did not have AVX, so we could only run TensorFlow version 1.15.0. Meaning, we had to downgrade our code to work with version 1.15 to run experiments in the Docker Swarm. The following is the result

of the experiment we ran to test the European Parliament corpus and the ANKI corpus.

IV. RESULT OF EXPERIMENTS

In the manual text cleaning stage, we had to replace “ $\alpha, \emptyset, \hat{a}$ ” with “ ae, eo and aa ”, as well as; “ $;$ ”; “ $()$ ”; and special information from Euro Parliament, had to be removed, otherwise, the text processing stage in python would generate various errors.

The following will first introduce our experiment with using Keras on ANKI and EuroP. Followed by Googles Neural Machine Translation TensorFlow on ANKI and EuroP.

A. Keras Neural Machine Translation

The Keras code uses LSTM. The inner workings of an LSTM [12] cell contain the function of learning; what to move to the long-term state and what to understand from it. The cell does this by self-loop gates, controlled by other hidden units. This update the weights based on the context rather than make them fixed. These self-loop weights are controlled by the Forget Gate (1) concept $f_i^{(t)}$ t is timestep and i is the cell, which often is set by a sigmoid activation unite.

$$f_i^{(t)} = \sigma \left(b_i^f + \sum_i U_{i,j}^f x_j^{(t)} + \sum_j W_{i,j}^f h_j^{(t-1)} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here $x^{(t)}$ is the input vector and $h^{(t)}$ is the current hidden layer tensor, \mathbf{b} is the biases, \mathbf{U} is the input weights and \mathbf{W} the recurrent weights, the sigma represents the gate.

The LSTM state is split into two state tensors: $\mathbf{h}_{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{c}_{(t)}$ where \mathbf{c} stands for cell. Here \mathbf{h} is the short-term memory and \mathbf{c} is the long-term memory. From a Keras programming concept, this means that we need to handle three variables as in Figure 1; an output, state_h and state_c.

The Keras code is based on the optimiser RMSprop:

$$v(w, t) := \gamma v(w, t - 1) + (1 - \gamma)(\nabla Q_i(w))^2 \quad (2)$$

```
encoder = LSTM(n_units, return_state=True, name='Encoder_lstm')
encoder_outputs, state_h, state_c = encoder(encoder_inputs)
encoder_states = [state_h, state_c]
```

Figure 1. Python programming of an LSTM cell, with Keras Functional API

With the activation function Softmax:

$$\sigma(\mathbf{z})_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}} \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, K \text{ and } \mathbf{z} = (z_1, \dots, z_K) \in \mathbb{R}^K \quad (3)$$

The Loss function is Categorical cross-entropy:

$$L_i = -\sum_j t_{i,j} \log(p_{i,j}) \quad (4)$$

B. Result of Keras on each corpus

Appendix 1 is an overview of the result from ANKI and EuroP corpus from 4.000 to 19.000 sentence run in Keras State-Of-The-Art NMT Seq2Seq model, with 10 epochs. As can be seen, the more sentences the more accurate the model becomes. However, the BLEU [19] score on ANKI and EuroP remained a 0. We modified the original code in several variations and could make the model accuracy higher, but when trying to use argmax on the output, the BLEU score did not improve for

EuroP. These novel variations will be published to GitHub, so others may learn from our code and avoid the issues we discovered.

Regarding the ANKI corpus, with 40 epoch and 4,000 sentences, it started to show signs of improvement and reached 30 BLEU point correctly translated sentences. At 100 epochs the BLEU score reached 75.

The EuroP corpus did not show any improvements, being a professional translation from a highly political environment, which contains longer complex sentences (see Table III) this could be the issue for these low BLEU score. Example of translation with the EuroP corpus at 19.000 sentences can be seen in Appendix 3.

It should also be noted that the ANKI corpus exposes a word, and short sentence multiple time. The EuroP only exposed a sentence once during the training, and many special words are only exposed a few times. The result for translation with the EuroP showed no improvement leading to the conclusion that the amount of text and complexity must be the issue. However, we wanted to test with Google TensorFlow framework to see if it could capture the EuroP corpus.

The Google NMT offers the Attention mechanism developed by [3] into the code to capture long sentences, with an alignment score function (5) to score the context vector \mathbf{c}_i .

$$c_i \sum_{j=1}^{T_x} \alpha_{ij} h_j \quad (5)$$

C. Google Tensorflow

The Google Tensorflow NMT can be found on: (https://colab.research.google.com/github/tensorflow/tensorflow/blob/r1.9/tensorflow/contrib/eager/python/examples/nmt_with_attention/nmt_with_attention.ipynb). The Google NMT uses GRU instead of LSTM as in the Keras version.

The GRU neuron is a simpler model that performs equally to LSTM [12]. Here the state vectors are reduced to a single vector $\mathbf{h}_{(t)}$. A single gate controls the forget- and input-gate. There is no output gate, the state vector outputted begins at every time step. Instead, an update gate controller, controls which are part of the prior state will be shown to the main output layer (see Equation 6).

$$h_i^{(t)} = u_i^{(t-1)} h_i^{(t-1)} + (1 + u_i^{(t-1)}) \sigma \left(b_i + \sum_j U_{i,j} x_j^{(t-1)} + \sum_j W_{i,j} r_j^{(t-1)} h_j^{(t-1)} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where \mathbf{u} stands for “update” and \mathbf{r} for “reset” gates the sigma represents the gate activation a logistic sigmoid. The gates computation can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} z_t &= \sigma(W_z \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ r_t &= \sigma(W_r \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ \tilde{h}_t &= \tanh(W \cdot [r_t * h_{t-1}, x_t]) \\ h_t &= (1 - z_t) * h_{t-1} + z_t * \tilde{h}_t \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The z_t is the update gate tensor is responsible for lowering the risk of vanishing gradient, since past information is moved to the future. The r_t is the reset gate tensor its function is to find information to “forget”. The \tilde{h}_t function is to pass the relevant information to h_t , which finally set the activation function of the cell.

From a TensorFlow programming concept, researchers would implement a GRU with two output variables: c^t and h^t . Since GRU’s introduction in 2014 by Cho et al. [2], it has become the industry standard for cell design replace many areas traditionally used by LSTM. The current state-of-the-art Neural Machine Translation applies, therefore, GRU and Attention onto the Encoder/Decoder framework.

1) Results of Googles NMT

Table IV shows that the ANKI corpus works well with the Google NMT tools. However, when we tried with the EuroP it performed significantly poor (see an example in Appendix 2).

The seq2seq of the text was correct and everything looked fine in the coding. However, when we looked at the files encoding in Notepad++, we could not find anything different except it contained CRLF as new-line. CR LF means "Carriage Return, Line Feed" - it is a leftover from DOS time. We changed this to LF or ‘\n’ this did not have any improvement on the BLEU score. We cleaned the first 10.000 sentences, meaning manually removed anything that was not pure text such as “(AT/889-08)” and remove complex sentences. The result was still no improvement in the translation. We presume that this is due to the long sentences’ length.

V. LONG SEQUENCES

Research in the field of Neural Machine Translation, are aware of the issue of long sentences and paragraph translation [1][16], which currently is a challenge for translation models to handle. The following is our attempt to improve the EuroP corpus long sentences. However, the major issue with the corpus is its “slight confound”, according to [20], since it has been concatenated as part of speech.

VI. ATTEMPT TO IMPROVE EURO P

Since the corpus EuroP was not performing, we wanted to test if combining ANKI with EuroP could have a positive effect on translation. The idea was to take the first 4.000 sentences from ANKI and then add 8000 from EuroP (see the result in Table IV). Thereby, give the NN a chance to learn simple sentences, and then to learn more long complex sentences. However, even with this combination, the model accuracy was a minor improvement of 0.02% with no increase in the BLEU score.

It should also be noted that increasing the number of epochs did not improve the BLEU score. An example with 200 epochs DK: “*Jeg erklærer Europa-Parlamentets session*” was translated into UK: “*i can raise again*”. Should have been: “*Resumption of the session*”. The “jeg” to “I” is correct.

Then we modified the Google NMT to focus on Multiheaded Attention (see Eq.8) based on the research from [18] and [17]. The result was a BLEU score of 0. At this point, we were wondering if the model had issues, so we tried with ANKI French corpus. The resulting BLEU score was 35 correct

translation for known words. The low score on Attention could be because of rich morphology agglutination in the Danish language, compared to the French to English translation. Meaning that, as the sentences become longer, so increases the morphology exponentially for Danish. The Danish vocabulary

TABLE IV
RESULT OF GOOGLES NMT – TESTED WITH KNOWN WORDS AND SENTENCES

Based on Google neural net model (DK-UK translation)	BLEU score	Epochs	Batch size	Neural Net size
ANKI – S-4000	98	10	64	1024
ANKI – S-8000	99	10	64	1024
ANKI – S-16000	100	10	64	1024
ANKI – S-19000	100	10	64	1024
EuroP – S-4000	0	10	64	1024
EuroP – S-8000	0	10	64	1024
EuroP – S-16000	0	10	64	1024
EuroP – S-19000	0.01	10	64	1024
ANKI & EuroP (s-4000 & S-8000)	0	10	64	1024

is around 1.4 times bigger than the English vocabulary.

We modified the corpus by taking the first 10 sentences. Broke them into smaller natural segments and exposed them four times to the Neural Network. The result for the EuroP was a significant improvement of the corpus. For that experiment, we used the GoogleNMT with the attention model from [18] and 200 epochs.

We then used the same 10 sentences, without natural-segmentation them, and exposed them four times to the Neural Network, the BLEU score dropped to 0.

The natural segmentation is not a feasible solution since it would require a human to manually go through all the 2 million lines of text in the EuroP corpus. An alternative is to modify the attention model itself.

The equation (10) shows the alignment score function from [18], which is part of the attention model (8). We tested with both version of the score function (9) and (10), but there was no improvement in the BLUE. We then modified the score function to (11).

$$\begin{aligned} &MultiHead(Q, K, V) \\ &= Concat(head^1 \dots head^h)W^O \text{ where } head^i \\ &= Attention(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VM_i^V) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In 2015 Luong et al [17] developed the below score function for the Attention:

$$MultiHead\ Score = S^T h_i \quad (9)$$

This was later modified by Vaswani et al (2017)[18] to:

$$MultiHead\ Score = \frac{S^T h_i}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (10)$$

Our modified version of the alignment score:

$$\text{MultiHead Score} = \frac{S^T h_i}{n} \quad (11)$$

The modified equation (11) perform, from a BLEU point, better compared to the Vaswani (2017) on the European Parliament corpus. Our test showed that with the Vaswani Multihead Score reached a maximum of 10 BLEU with 200 epochs, our modified Multihead Score reached up to 13 BLEUs on the English to Danish Translation with EuroP corpus.

Applying ANKI corpus with equation (10) the score was between 33-100 BLEU points. In comparison, our equation (11) scored between 38-100 points on small sentences (See Appendix 4). On large sentences with the ANKI corpus, both (10) and (11) started to lower the BLEU score, equation (10) between 5-10 points, our modified version (11) scores 0-12 points on the same long sentences.

By removing the square root from the dot product scaling, the model seems to be better at capturing more regions in the gradient. Thereby, we expect that the softmax function can better capture long sequences in languages with high morphology as the Danish language. This requires further testing and the following we present our suggestion for future research into the European Parliament data.

VII. CONCLUSION

The European Parliament corpus for Danish to English translation presents a challenge for Neural Machine Translation models, due to its concatenated as part of speech from a political translated corpus.

Our attempt to improve the Danish to English translation showed promising result by modifying the attention alignment score function. Our modified alignment score indicates that there are possibilities for improvement inside the model itself to aid Danish to English translation.

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APPENDIX 1

OVERVIEW OF KERAS TRANSLATION WITH ANKI AND EURO P

ANKI	EuroP
<p>4.000 sentences loss: 0.8049 - acc: 0.7630 - val_loss: 0.9836 - val_acc: 0.7104</p> <p>model accuracy, with 4.000 samples</p> <p>BLEU Score: 0</p>	
<p>8.000 sentences loss: 0.6406 - acc: 0.8061 - val_loss: 0.8658 - val_acc: 0.7364</p> <p>model accuracy</p> <p>BLEU score: 0</p>	
<p>16.000 sentences loss: 0.3696 - acc: 0.8886 - val_loss: 0.6163 - val_acc: 0.8139</p> <p>model accuracy, with 16.000 samples</p> <p>Blue score: 0</p>	
<p>19.000 sentences loss: 0.4002 - acc: 0.8784 - val_loss: 0.7893 - val_acc: 0.7617</p> <p>model accuracy, with 19.000 samples</p> <p>BLEU score: 0</p>	

